

DOUBLE STANDARDS IN WARS ARE THE TARGET OF FICTION (IN BAHAA TAHER'S 'LOVE IN EXILE' NOVEL)

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Abstract. *The article touches upon the creativity of Egyptian writer Bahaa Taher and thoroughly studies Taher's 'Love in Exile' novel (1995). This novel is a blend of political realities and romantic feelings.*

"Love in Exile" depicts fate of a journalist who could not identify himself. Separated from his family, far away from his home, Motherland, the one who wants to find consolation, to forget and be forgotten, sets up a relationship with a problematic one as him. The things happening around and inside don't allow them to be happy.

In his love story the writer skillfully depicts the bloody war scenes, destroyed settlements, heaped human bodies, innocent people who suffered from hunger and misery within the real historical fact and geographical locations. Taher exposes bitter truth, the real saboteur faces behind the scenes, condemns injustice, the division of people into the "classes":

The article examines Taher's multilayered variations on the themes of exile, war, failed dreams and love in this novel.

Although the book has not been written as a war novel, it is a reminiscent of Erich Maria Remark, Ernest Hemingway style. His "Love in Exile" novel smells gunpowder, blood, dead bodies like in Remark, Hemingway's works. So, the changing plot, location, time, and heroes did not change the terrible war reality.

In general, Taher does not write war novels, but almost all his works include the war relics and its painful results. Today's realities reflected in Taher's novels - the weakness of intercultural dialogue, the collision of religions, world powers' management of the world for their purposes, double standards, the artificial epidemics for the benefit of the pharmaceutical industry, faked wars and political problems to test new weapons and economic crises pushes out his works from oriental frames and makes them universally significant and topical.

Keywords: *Arabic literature, Double standards, Bahaa Taher, Egypt, Love in Exile, War, Emigrants*

Body: Ongoing tensions, never-ending wars in the East, that have occupied the world's political agenda, remain to produce an unending theme for literature. Even a short study into the history of world literature will show the sufficiency (abundance) of the battle scenes, folk tales full of courage, colorful poetry patterns in the Arab literature. Wars remain topical in the Arab literature for over decades, despite surviving the period of ignorance and the roots of classic literature in some respects. There are indeed changes in genre, plot, characters, and weapons, but no change in the painful consequences that the war produces, in particular the human loss.

The primary explanation for the case can be hot temper of Arabs, as well as special importance of features like morality, honesty, and honor for them.

There is a very rich list of the authors "writing about war" and the books about war in the Arab literature. But we would like to mention here Bahaa Taher, a writer, and his "Love in Exile" novel.

The works of the writer, who achieved great success by being honored with State Award of Merit in Literature, which is Egypt's highest literary award, in 1998, Italian Giuseppe Acerbi Prize for "Aunt Safiyya and the Monastery" novel in 2000, International Prize for Arabic Fiction for "Sunset Oasis" novel in 2008, have been translated into several languages and popularized him outside the Arab East (about Bahaa Taher).

Descriptive Paragraph: Taher's "Love in Exile" novel is a very example to clearly mirror the author's literary creativity. He is considered to be one of the bright representatives of the "New wave"

emerging in the Egyptian literature in the 1960s. Nervousness inherent to the "New wave" representatives is well observed on Taher's heroes, who live the "love in exile". The atmosphere of shattered dreams, hopes and unrealized expectations affects the views and speech of the heroes. The writer's suspense is cognized throughout the story, while optimistic tunes almost bend the neck to pessimistic gamma. At the same time, a sense of fanaticism is never lost, hope does not die. Revolutions, coups, reforms, elections do not live up their expectations. The reality of Egypt and problems of heroes remain unresolved regardless of the change in political regimes and as a result, we witness that the sentiments of 1960s still conquering the "exiled" heroes. The writer uses concrete and realistic documentary to bolster his idea, which helps him to make the novel more exciting. With regard to massacres in Sabra, Shatilda and Deyr Yasin villages the author brings real documentary facts with an ultimate goal to convey the major idea – the double standards that countries demonstrate towards the problems. Even, speaking of the civil position, he compares the ordinary facts:

Death of one child is a death to the whole world of course. And yet no one will ask you how many children died in Galilee – five or ten? And how many thousands of children did Israel exterminate in Lebanon and before that in Palestine? And why not? You are not alone!

In the morning, the news would report hundreds of dead and wounded every day in the city under siege, but in the evening the television would carry a somber ceremony full of religious rites and tears and anger for the burial of four Israeli soldiers who fell in the "war" (Taher, 2010, p.133-134).

Or another quote from the novel: "As many as 20,000 people were killed and 50,000 were injured in return for the assassination of the Israeli ambassador in London and for restoring peace in Galilee" (Taher, 2010, p.146).

In another part of the novel, the writer once again cries out the bitter truth with irony to the world community, advocates of human rights and democracy: "Thousands of killed Arabs are simply a number. But one killed Israeli is tragedy and terror..." (Taher, 2010, p.146).

Taher's "Love in Exile" novel is a blend of political realities and romantic feelings. By the way, the title of the novel is the same with the story of well-known French writer Andre Maurois (1885-1967) "Love in Exile". However, this similarity limits itself with only the names of the works and events which are taken place out of the place of birth of heroes for some reasons. Maurois' heroes live the love purely in writer's literary style, there is no room for deep, sincere feelings, but there is only the atmosphere of "mercenary love adventures" in the story (Maurois, 1992, 288).

But Taher's love in exile is pure and altruistic.

Based on the feelings of love, Taher's novel presents a plot telling the war. "Love in Exile" depicts fate of a journalist who could not identify himself. Separated from his family, far away from his home, Motherland, the one who wants to find consolation, to forget and be forgotten, sets up a relationship with a problematic one as him. The things happening around and inside don't allow them to be happy.

In his love story the writer skillfully depicts the bloody war scenes, destroyed settlements, heaped human bodies, innocent people who suffered from hunger and misery within the real historical fact and geographical locations. Taher exposes bitter truth, the real saboteur faces behind the scenes, condemns injustice, the division of people into the "classes":

"Both sides consider itself just in the war between Iraq and Iran, "countless keys of heaven" are distributed, the blood flows instead of water. In war in Lebanon, a nation chosen by God annihilates a nation not favored. The army commander declares that "A good Arab is dead Arab!" That happens because the killer is always better, and above all" (Taher, 2010, p.121).

In his novel, Taher condemns the western countries, the United States that call for democracy, human rights protection in their own language. Bernard, a major character, writes: "Our free country has been stricken by a strange malady these days. It has become mute and hasn't uttered a word about the crimes against human rights, so long as those crimes were committed by the Hebrew State..."

Israel is taboo. Israel cannot be touched and everything that country does is good” (Taher, 2010, p.121). Bernard, who is a journalist by profession, conveys the truth with irony, saying that ones who speak against it, seek truth and justice have been accused of anti-Semitism, subjected to persecution.

In addition, from time to time the reader remains face to face with the war scenes described very idyllic: “Ladies and gentlemen, in twenty years of work this is report I had hoped I would never make”.

His voice trembles as he says, “This is the first time the camera has entered the Sabra refugee camp after the massacre of the Palestinians over the last few days” (Taher, 2010, p.121).

After that the camera moves around in silence. It moves through narrow alleys in the minds of destroyed houses from which are jutting twisted steel rods and remnants of broken furniture, but there are no signs of any life or movement. Then the camera takes its time as it takes long shots:

Piles of corpses are strewn over the ground. Corpses are behind corpses and corpses next to corpses. A pile of mixed corpses of men and women are lying on their faces and on their sides and on their backs. Another pile of women and children are sprawled on their backs, legs wide apart.

A third pile of men’s corpses, swollen as if the skins and clothes will burst any moment.

The upper body of a corpse stuck in the rubble, hanging down with its head bowed to the ground, its neck cut widthwise from behind.

Two little girls stand next to each other, with their bare upper bodies. Someone had tried to cover their lower bodies with a flattened tin but was not successful. The little legs protrude, wide apart.

The camera shakes as it captures them and zooms in a little. One of the girls has two holes filled with clotted blood where the eyes had been.

A pile of corpses with outstretched arms next to a destroyed wall as if they were climbing on top of each other. In the wall are billet holes and vertical lines of blood: wounded fingers clinging before falling.

Corpses looking as if prostrating next to a white horse fallen on its side, its belly slashed open, its rump swollen, and its tail still convulsive. An old gray-haired man stands next to it with his thin legs jutting from a white galabiyya. Next to him a crutch towards which his hand is extended. In his head, a bloody hole.

Large flies are sitting on the horse, and many flies on the corpses (Taher, 2010, p.134).

In the following quote, a dream of the narrator-main character of the story is not only a war nightmare, but it also is a dream of political games, indifference: “Asleep at night I see a woman and a man running in a terror under the gun projectiles, they are holding a human hand wrapped in a newspaper, the blood flows through the newspaper. Where and why are they taking the hand? In the dream, I see Israeli soldiers, carrying along under their bayonets the young with the eyes and arms tied behind. I say to myself: everything will change tomorrow, it cannot continue like this. If Israel acts in this way just because of injury of one person – the ambassador, then we ought to erupt as a volcano for the hundreds of people killed every day. It is impossible that a sense of dignity have been lost forever. After all, the blood flows in our vessels, not water and the volcano to erupt tomorrow has not come yet!

However, in the morning, the ceasefire was declared for the second time, then a third time ... for the fifth time. The American delegate is coming... Ceasefire for the seventh time... Ambulance cars accompanied by a loud signal are speeding along the burning streets. Israel has stopped the supply of water and electricity to Beirut. Messy-haired, barefoot girl fills an iron can from the dirty pool.

Nothing happens outside Beirut” (Taher, 2010, p.136).

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Conclusion: In general, Taher does not write war novels, but almost all his works include the war relics and its painful results. Today's realities reflected in Taher's novels - the weakness of intercultural dialogue, the collision of religions, world powers' management of the world for their purposes, double standards, the artificial epidemics for the benefit of the pharmaceutical industry, faked wars and political problems to test new weapons and economic crises pushes out his works from oriental frames and makes them universally significant and topical.

Taher noted in this novel that despite Europe and the U.S. express concern over the human rights violation, and torture of prisoners in prisons, they demonstrate indifference towards the people killed in the armed conflict zones, and in the armistice breaches every day. They only content themselves with issuing distorted reports, empty statements through inefficient mediation of international organizations and societies, as well as NGOs.

USED LITERATURE:

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